

Microestimation of Riboflavine with Some Organic Reagents

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Riboflavine has been colorimetrically estimated using (1) methyl-dopa, (2) *ortho*-aminophenol, and (3) hydroquinone, as colour forming agents. The proposed method is sensitive, and does not suffer from interference from compounds commonly present in pharmaceutical preparations.

RIBOFLAVINE (7,8-dimethyl-10-ribityl-isoalloxazine) is a B-complex factor and is mostly formulated with other B-complex factors and other vitamins. Its simple and fast estimation is, therefore, very important. Reported colorimetric methods of estimation of riboflavine are by mercuric sulphate¹, by Cu(II)triphenylphosphine complex² and by chromotropic acid³. Mercuric sulphate method requires very high concentration of riboflavine. The Cu(II)triphenylphosphine method includes a tedious process of the preparation of reagent and dilution with methanol. In chromotropic acid method also, high concentration of riboflavine is required. Further the method is lengthy, and suffers from interference of vitamin C.

In the present work we have reported colorimetric estimation of riboflavine using methyl-dopa, *ortho*-aminophenol and hydroquinone.

Experimental

All the reagents used were of analytical grade. Riboflavine standard was prepared by dissolving in distilled water 50 mg of the compound previously dried for 2 hours at 105°. To this was added 1 ml of 0.1N NaOH to clear the solution followed by 1 ml of glacial acetic acid to preserve the solution. The volume was made to 250 ml with distilled water to give 200 µg/ml of riboflavine solution. Ten ml of the stock solution was diluted to 100 ml to give 20 µg/ml.

The sample solution was prepared by dissolving and diluting the sample to give a concentration of 20 µg/ml. The colour coating in the case of tablets was removed by rubbing the tablet with cotton wet with water and/or organic solvent.

Comparative data of the estimation conditions of riboflavine with the 3 reagents are given in Table 1.

Assay Procedures :

(i) *Methyl-dopa* : In clean, dry 10 ml graduated test-tubes 3 ml of standard solution and 3 ml sample solution was taken separately. 5 ml of 0.4 M ammonia and 0.5 ml of reagent was added and diluted to the mark with water. Absorbance was taken at 447 nm against a reagent blank after about 10 minutes.

(ii) *OAP* : In 10 ml graduated test-tubes 3 ml of standard solution and 3 ml of sample solution was taken, along with 1.5 ml of reagent and 2 ml of 4 M ammonia and diluted to the mark with water. At 443 nm absorbance was measured against a reagent blank after about 10 minutes.

(iii) *Hydroquinone* : 3 ml of each standard and sample was mixed with 0.6 ml reagent and 5 ml of 0.1M ammonia. The volume was made to 10 ml with

TABLE 1

Reagent	Reagent concentration	Alkali concentration	Stability (min.)	λ_{max} nm.	Beer's Law range µg/ml	Extinction coefficient of the coloured species $\times 10^{-4}$
Methyl-dopa	0.5 ml of 0.1% (0.1M HCl)	5 ml of 0.4M NH ₄ OH	30	447	3 to 15	1.15
OAP	1.5 ml of 0.4% (Alcoholic)	2 ml of 4M NH ₄ OH	50	448	2 to 12	1.4
Hydroquinone	0.6 ml of 0.1% (Aqueous)	5 ml of 0.1M NH ₄ OH	40	453	2 to 15	1.3

TABLE 2—ANALYSIS OF RIBOFLAVINE IN MARKETED SAMPLES

Preparation	Vit. B ₂ present (mg)	Vit. B ₂ found (mg)			% Recovery			Vit. B ₂ found (mg) by A.O.A.C. Method ^a
		Methyl dopa	OAP	Hydroquinone	Methyl dopa	OAP	Hydroquinone	
Tablet (A)	16.6	18.3	18.1	17.9	101	99.8	99.5	18
Tablet (B)	2	2.2	2.1	2.15	100.2	99.8	101	2.25
Capsule (A)	10	11.1	10.8	11.2	98.9	99.6	99.8	10.8
Capsule (B)	10	11.8	11.6	11.7	99.9	100.2	98.9	11.6
Syrup (A)	1	1.55	1.57	1.6	99.5	99.3	100.3	1.58
Syrup (B)	2	3.1	3.2	3.15	100.5	98.9	99.2	3.2

water and absorbance was measured against a reagent blank at 453 nm after about 5 minutes.

$$\text{mg of riboflavine} = \text{At} \times \text{S} \times \text{D} / \text{As} \times 1000$$

where, At = absorbance of sample, As = absorbance of standard, D = Dilution factor, and S = μg of standard/ml.

Study of Interference : Interference of the following compounds was studied. Figures in brackets indicate minimum fold excess of species tolerated. Thiamine-(8), Niacinamide-(2), Pyridoxine-(5), Ca-pantothenate-(3), Ascorbic acid-(33), Ca-phosphate-(25), MgO-(15), MnSO₄-(1), Phosphorous-(6), CuSO₄-(1), ZnSO₄-(0.5), B₁₂-(0.004), Folic acid-(1), Ca-glycerophosphate-(65), and Mn-glycerophosphate-(8).

Discussion

Results in Table-1 indicate that all the 3 reagents employed in the estimation of riboflavine are nearly

equally sensitive. The colour species formed are sufficiently stable for their absorbance measurements and results are highly reproducible. The simplicity of the proposed method lies in the fact that the colour development is fast and preparation of reagent solutions are very simple and solutions can be stored for several days. The method is also free from interference of ascorbic acid and other compounds commonly associated with riboflavine in pharmaceutical preparations.

References

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